

THE IMPORTANCE OF TERMINOLOGY IN THE FIELD OF LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *Terminology is of particular importance in the field of linguistics. It is known that language and society are always closely connected with each other. The role of the field of terminology is important in increasing the vocabulary of a language. The purpose of this dissertation is to study the origins and stages of development of the field of terminology.*

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As you know, these terms are one of the main means of expressing national traditions and customs of the people. The word terminus comes from the Latin word *terminus*, which means limit, boundary. A word or phrase that is a clear and stable expression of a specific concept characteristic of a field of science, technology or profession; term, for example, botanical terms and jewelry terms. We can call these terms a mirror of history.

After all, through them, science records all the events that occurred in the history of mankind. For example, conquests experienced in the past and the process of globalization have had a great influence on science, culture, especially terminology. That is why today in circulation there are terms borrowed from different languages or created from internal representations of the language. According to the famous terminologist G. O. Vinokur: “Terms do not appear, but are invented and created when the need for them is felt.” Therefore, terms are words that are created in connection with a certain need.

Linguistic scientist R. Donierov: “Neither a specific science nor technology in general, therefore their terms are not a product of the creativity of a specific people. They represent a collection of objective existence, collected, known and studied by all the peoples of the world,” he says. Many linguists have different views on the concept of this term. Scientists distinguish between the concepts of “term”, “terminus”, “istila”.

For example, according to A. Madvaliev, “The word term refers to words and phrases used in any field or branch of science, and the word terminus refers to conventionally assigned names, including geographical ones, which we consider appropriate to apply in a broad sense to names of objects and toponyms.

It is inappropriate to use the word istila in the sense in which the term is used as a name for concepts of modern science and technology that are increasingly developing. But the use of this word in texts on historical topics should not raise any objections.

Terminology is a field of study that is closely related to the concept of a term. The field of terminology is one of the most important areas of linguistics, which includes words and phrases, terms, studies their origin, stages of development and renewal. This subject is also a branch of linguistics that studies vocabulary related to a specific and specific field.

The main object of such research is special lexical units or special lexemes and, of course, first of all terms. Terminology is important because it is the study of vocabulary specific to each

area. He analyzes and studies the origin, formal structure, meaning and functional aspects of words. It would not be an exaggeration to say that although the stage of development of terminology goes back a long time, the level of its study never decreases.

Because the language of a nation is constantly developing, progressing and changing, and as a result of this, new words begin to penetrate into the language or different words from another language change and are assimilated. As a result, further research on terminology is needed. As humanity grows and develops and creates a new way of life, the field of linguistic terminology becomes increasingly rich.

If we consider the initial stages of the emergence and development of terminology, then, although it has been used since ancient times, it began to be studied as a separate science at the beginning of the 18th century, studying and analyzing the history of the origin of words.

Interest in the field of terminology has been one of the most pressing topics in the spotlight of world linguistics for several years now. Among world linguists, Uzbek linguists also paid great attention and interest to the field of terminology. Conventionally, the stages of formation of Uzbek terminology can be divided into three stages:

1. VII-X centuries. – stage of Turkic language terminology;
2. XI-XIV centuries. – stage of terminology of the ancient Turkic language;
3. XV-XX centuries. – stage of terminology of the Old Uzbek literary language.

In addition, the terminology of the Uzbek language was formed during the period of independence, and thus the field of Uzbek terminology is being formed every day. Of course, it is no secret to any of us that the field of terminology occupies a special place and position in the construction of the modern Uzbek literary language.

The role of terminology in the vocabulary of a language is significant and helps to increase vocabulary. Terminology makes up a large part of the vocabulary of all languages, so terminological science continues to develop at a rapid pace, since terminology allows the creation of new words in the language.

Linguists have given different definitions of the term. Logicians argue that a term is a collection of descriptions (or descriptions) relating to a particular object and the words that apply it.

The terms can be divided into two groups according to science and profession:

- a) scientific terms
- b) professional terms

Words related to science, art, literature and other fields are called scientific terms. These terms can mean one thing in one field and another in another, although they represent the same thing or object, they can be used in different ways.

Trade words are professional terms and include a number of terms such as ranching, pottery, hunting, construction, shoemaking, carpentry, butchery. It is actually very difficult to understand the exact meaning of one-word terms. In this case, it is correct to make a decision based on the context and its content.

REFERENCES

1. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Volume 5. Tashkent: G. Gulom Publishing House, 2023.

2. Vinokur G.O. About some phenomena of word formation in Russian technical terminology. // Proceedings of MIF. Volume 5. Collection of articles on linguistics. - Moscow, 1939. - P. 24.
3. Doniyorov R. From the history of scientific and technical terms of the Uzbek language. - T.: Nauka, 1973. - B. 4.
4. Madvaliev A. Questions of Uzbek terminology and lexicography. – T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2017. – B. 29.